

Studies in Reductions with V(II) Sulphate-II Potentiometric Titration of Molybdate with V(II)

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Direct and reverse potentiometric titrations of V(II) against Mo(VI) have been performed in the atmosphere of nitrogen. When V(II) is taken in the cell, only sulphuric acid medium is essential, whereas with Mo(VI) in the cell some amount of phosphoric acid along with sulphuric acid is needed for fast reduction. Both in the direct and reverse titrations, only one potential break was found in the titration curve corresponding to 3 moles of V(II) per mole of Mo(VI). As the reaction is almost quantitative, the titrations may be used for the determinations of molybdate in solution.

Reductions of Mn(III) and Ce(IV) by V(II) have already been reported by us¹. Here both the oxidants have only one possible lower oxidation state, whereas the reductant has more than one higher oxidation states. The oxidant Mo(VI) can be reduced to Mo(V) or Mo(III) or both. Stable ionic species of Mo(IV) are not known to exist though it has been reported in some solid state² at high temperature. Some information are available on Mo(VI) reductions by Cr(II)³⁻⁵, Ti(III)⁶⁻⁷, Sn(II)⁸⁻¹², Fe(II) and Hg(I)¹³. Study with V(II) does not appear to have been done by the earlier workers. The present potentiometric investigations were therefore undertaken to carry out a quantitative study of the equilibria involved in the interaction of Mo(VI) with V(II) ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadium (II) solution: It was prepared, stored and standardised as reported earlier¹.

Molybdenum (VI) solution: Approximately 0.1 N solutions were prepared by dissolving sodium molybdate (B.D.H.) in air free water. It was standardised by the usual standard method¹⁴ using Jon's reductor.

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Apparatus : In view of the instability of vanadium (II) solution the potentiometric titrations were done in a constant atmosphere of oxygen free nitrogen. Accordingly a 250 ml. pyrex flask fitted with a rubber cork having five holes, was used to accommodate the electrode, the salt bridge, the tip of the burette and inlet and outlet tube for nitrogen. The reference electrode was saturated calomel and platinum was used as an indicator electrode. Agar Agar gel saturated with potassium chloride was used as salt bridge.

The cell was deoxygenated by passing nitrogen for 15 minutes before taking a known volume of the oxidant [molybdenum (VI)] or reductant [vanadium (II)]. The requisite amount of sulphuric acid and air free water was added so as to make the desired acidity and also an initial constant volume was maintained. Vanadium (II) or molybdenum (VI) solution was added from the burette and the stable potentials were noted after each addition. Experimental results are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE 1

10 ml. of $M/100 \text{ Na}_2\text{MoO}_4$ (0.918) in X (N) Sulphuric acid
 \equiv Y ml. of $M/10$ Vanadium (II) solution (0.87).

Sl No.	X	Y	Moles of Vanadium(II) per mole of molybdate solution
1	6N	3.20	3.033
2	2N	3.20	3.033
3	N	3.15	2.985
4	N/2	3.20	3.033
5	N/10	3.20	3.033

TABLE 2

10 ml. of $M/50$ Vanadium (II) solution (0.6) in X (N) Sulphuric acid
 \equiv Y ml. of $M/20$ Molybdate solution (0.918).

Sl.No.	X	Y	Moles of Vanadium (II) per mole of molybdate solution
1	6N	0.85	3.076
2	N	0.87	3.005
3	N/2	0.87	3.005
4	N/10	0.87	3.005

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

When Mo(VI) solution was taken in the cell containing only sulphuric acid, from visual observations the reaction seemed to be slow and too much time was needed for the indicator electrode to attain stable potential. But on addition of about 1 ml. of phosphoric acid, the reaction was fast as Mo(VI) becomes more reducible probably due to the formation of phosphomolybdate complex¹⁵, and stable potentials were obtained in 10–15 minutes (20–25 minutes at the inflexion point). On the other hand with V(II) solution in the cell, phosphoric acid was not needed for the fast reaction, as initial high concentrations of strong reducing agent V(II) was sufficient for the purpose. Possibly due to this fact, with the consumption

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of V(II) in the course of titration the time required to attain stable potential increased. Both in the direct and reverse titrations, only one potential break was found in the titration curve corresponding to 3 moles V(II) per mole of Mo(VI). As expected at the inflexion point the polarity of indicator electrode changed with respect to saturated calomel as reference electrode (see figure). Initially the indicator electrode was -ve when V(II) solution was in the cell and +ve when Mo(VI) solution was taken in the cell.

Fig. 1

On the basis of oxidation potentials of Mo and V species given by Latimer¹⁶,

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$3\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4(\text{aq}) + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e} = 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$+ (\text{MoO}_2)_2\text{MoO}_4,$... Ca + 0.6
$\text{H}_2\text{MoO}_4(\text{aq}) + 2\text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{MoO}_2^+$	$+ 2\text{H}_2\text{O},$... Ca + 0.4
$\text{MoO}_2^+ + 4\text{H}^+ + 2\text{e} = \text{Mo}^{+++}$	$+ 2\text{H}_2\text{O},$... Ca + 0.0
$\text{V}^{+++} + \text{e} = \text{V}^{++}$... -0.255
$\text{VO}^{++} + 2\text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{V}^{+++} + \text{H}_2\text{O},$... +0.361
$\text{V}(\text{OH})^+_4 + 2\text{H}^+ + \text{e} = \text{VO}^{++} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O},$... +1.00

the reaction may take place according to the following equations :

As per available literature¹⁷ Mo(V) and Mo(III) ions may also exist as MoO⁺⁺⁺ and MoO⁺ respectively. Thus equation I to IV can be written accordingly, but without any change in the stoichiometry.

Mo(V) and V(IV) cannot exist so long (VII) is present in excess, as V(II) can reduce both the species. Thus when V(II) is taken in the cell, only one potential break is possible in the titration curve corresponding to the equation (I) which we have actually observed. On the other hand when Mo(VI) solution is taken in the cell, more than one potential breaks are possible corresponding to stoichiometry II and IV or III, IV and V. But then either set of reactions seem to be taking place with almost the same equilibrium constant and hence the overall reaction will be represented as in equation (I) with a single potential break as observed experimentally. The existence of green or brownish green colours¹⁸ at the point of inflexion in each case indicates the presence of V(III) and Mo(III) species. The fact that before the inflexion point is reached, sometimes there is a momentary appearance of blue colour which leads us to conclude that there may be formation of V(IV) and Mo(V) species in the intermediate steps as suggested in the above equations. The different amount of sulphuric and phosphoric acids used does not affect the stoichiometry. As the reaction takes place at ordinary temperature and is almost quantitative, the titrations may be used for the determination of molybdate in solutions.

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